

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL COMMUNICATIONS FOR PROMOTING BRANDS ON SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS

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ABSTRACT

The effectiveness of digital communications is a key factor in the successful promotion of brands on social media platforms. This issue is especially relevant in the context of the rapid development of digital technologies, which create new opportunities for interaction with the audience and strengthening brand positions. However, despite extensive research on social media marketing, there remains a knowledge gap regarding the comparative effectiveness of different platforms and their content strategies in driving audience engagement and conversions. Existing studies often focus on individual platforms or specific digital marketing techniques without a comprehensive cross-platform analysis of digital communication effectiveness.

This study addresses this gap by analyzing the effectiveness of digital strategies in promoting brands on Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and LinkedIn. Special attention is paid to key performance indicators such as the Engagement Rate (ER), Click-Through Rate (CTR), and conversions, as well as their dependence on content strategies and platform specifics. The aim of the study is to assess the impact of digital communications on the effectiveness of brand promotion in social media and identify key factors that contribute to increasing the rate of interaction with the audience. The study employs quantitative analysis, sociological surveys, comparative analysis, and correlation analysis to provide a data-driven evaluation of digital marketing strategies.

The results demonstrate that TikTok achieves the highest ER due to interactive content and active engagement from a younger audience, while Instagram remains dominant in the premium segment due to its visually appealing content. Facebook maintains a stable engagement rate due to its broad user base but lacks innovative content formats, and LinkedIn proves effective for professional communication. Conversely, Twitter faces challenges due to declining user activity and engagement.

The academic novelty of this research lies in its comprehensive cross-platform analysis of digital communication effectiveness, considering algorithmic operations, audience behavior, and content strategies. This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by providing insights into the optimal digital marketing strategies across different platforms and industries.

Prospects for future research include analyzing the adaptation of emerging content formats to platform-specific requirements, assessing the role of micro-influencers in audience engagement, and forecasting the evolution of digital communications until 2028.

Keywords: *Digital Communications, Social Media, Branded Content, TikTok, Instagram, Interaction, KPI, Conversions.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness of digital communications is one of the key aspects of modern marketing, which ensures the successful promotion of brands and their integration into the consumers' lives. It involves not only the creation of high-quality content but also the use of analytical data to optimize the strategy, increase the ER, and achieve high conversion rates. The effectiveness of digital strategy is becoming particularly relevant in a world where social media has become one of the main communication channels. However, despite the growing importance of social media in marketing, there is a lack of comprehensive studies that compare the effectiveness of digital communication strategies across different platforms. While existing research explores various aspects of social media engagement, many studies focus on single-platform effectiveness rather than cross-platform comparisons. This study fills this gap by systematically analyzing digital marketing strategies on Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and LinkedIn, assessing how different content formats, engagement tactics, and platform-specific algorithms influence brand promotion success. By identifying key factors that drive audience interaction and conversions, this research provides marketers and businesses valuable insights into optimizing their digital communication strategies. Furthermore, as social media algorithms and user behaviours evolve, this study offers timely and relevant data to help brands adapt to emerging trends and maximize their online presence. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and LinkedIn enable brands to engage with diverse audiences through personalized content and adapt to changing consumer behaviour. Key indicators such as engagement rate, CTR, and conversions are key performance indicators. TikTok engages a younger audience through interactive video content, LinkedIn through professional communication, Facebook provides broad reach, and Instagram leads with visually appealing content. Analysis of the dynamics of such indicators as ER and CTR for 2022–2024 gives grounds to assess the effectiveness of various digital strategies. Particular attention should be paid to studying the impact of interactive content and micro-influencers on audience engagement, as well as adapting content to the specifics of each platform.

Although digital marketing on social media has been widely studied, most research focuses on individual platforms rather than conducting a comparative cross-platform analysis. For instance,

the authors [1] examined influencer-follower relationships but emphasized influencer marketing rather than engagement strategies. Similarly, the researchers [2] provided a broad review of digital marketing but did not compare audience interaction across different platforms.

The authors [3] explored television advertising's impact on online word-of-mouth (WOM), but this does not reflect real-time engagement on social media. The explorers [4] analyzed cause-related marketing through influencers, yet their work lacked platform-specific engagement analysis. The authors [5] examined influencers' role in public relations but did not address engagement variations across platforms.

The researchers [6] also focused on Instagram marketing, overlooking other platforms like TikTok, Twitter, and LinkedIn. The authors [7] investigated social media's role in the creator economy but did not evaluate how brands can optimize engagement metrics across multiple platforms.

This study fills these gaps by conducting a comparative analysis of digital communication effectiveness across multiple platforms, focusing on key performance indicators (ER, CTR, and conversions). Unlike prior research, which often examines individual platforms or influencer marketing in isolation, this study provides a broader perspective on engagement trends across Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and LinkedIn. It investigates how interactive content, micro-influencers, and algorithmic changes shape brand engagement and audience interaction.

By addressing these research gaps, this study contributes to the field by offering data-driven insights into cross-platform digital marketing strategies and identifying best practices for optimizing brand presence on social media. The findings will help businesses develop effective content strategies tailored to platform-specific strengths, ensuring maximum audience engagement and visibility.

Aim: assess the effectiveness of digital communications in promoting brands on social media platforms.

Empirical objectives:

1. Analyse the dynamics of key indicators of digital communications effectiveness (ER, CTR, conversions) on five major platforms (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, LinkedIn) for 2022–2024;

2. Assess the impact of the use of interactive content and micro-influencers on the rate of interaction with the audience;

3. Identify the main factors that affect the effectiveness of digital communications in different industries and on different platforms;

4. Provide recommendations for adapting content strategies to ensure the brands' success on social media.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of the literature on the effectiveness of digital communications in promoting brands on social platforms reveals significant achievements, as well as limitations. The authors [1] emphasize the importance of influencer marketing, but underestimate the role of SEO and content marketing. The researchers [2] emphasize analytical approaches, but do not take into account differences between platforms. The authors [3] emphasize the role of interaction with content, but do not cover current trends such as AR and video formats. The researchers [4] study TikTok, but their analysis is reduced to this platform. The scientists [5] argue that influencers build trust, but do not take into account the difference between brand types. The researchers [6] suggest combining creative content with an analytical approach, but do not provide real-world examples. The authors [7] focus on LinkedIn for corporate brands but do not consider other platforms. The study [8] confirms the importance of active engagement but does not consider the differences in impact on different audiences.

The researchers [9] consider multiple platforms but do not focus on integration between them. The scientists [10] emphasize the importance of video content but do not consider the specifics of format choice for different brands. The authors [11] analyse campaign effectiveness without considering changes in consumer behaviour oriented towards digital platforms. The researchers [12] emphasize the importance of relationship building but do not consider the challenges of the digital age. The authors [13] focus on the protective image of a brand in crisis situations, requiring a more detailed analysis across platforms. The study [14] examines consumer behaviour but does not consider new platforms like TikTok. The research [15] emphasizes trust but does not consider interactivity and personalization of content. The scientists [16] emphasize the regularity of publications for small businesses, without considering adaptation to new platforms. The authors [17] emphasize the importance of adaptation, but do not consider the needs of the audience. The

researchers [18] point out the importance of emotional engagement but do not consider content personalization. The scientists [19] focus on inspirational content but do not consider its impact across platforms.

The study [20] examines interactive content but does not take into account algorithmic changes. The authors [21] emphasize brand co-creation but do not discuss the risks of negative content. The researchers [22] point to the effectiveness of visual content but do not consider its impact on less engaged audiences. The scientists [23] compare platform effectiveness but do not account for algorithmic changes. The authors [24] examine emotional content but do not account for new formats such as video and Stories. The researchers [25] focus on Facebook likes but do not account for the impact of algorithms. The authors [26] emphasize social values but do not consider different types of brands and markets. The scientists [27] point out the need for unique strategies for each platform, but require a deeper analysis of campaigns. The researchers [28] emphasize the importance of strategic planning, but do not take into account the impact of new technologies.

Previous studies have extensively examined the role of influencer marketing, content strategies, and engagement metrics across various social media platforms. Research has demonstrated that personalized content, interactive elements, and video formats significantly enhance engagement levels [1, 2, 10]. Additionally, studies highlight the growing importance of micro-influencers in building brand trust and fostering long-term consumer relationships [5, 6, 15]. However, most prior works have either focused on individual platforms or analyzed engagement strategies in isolation without conducting a comparative, cross-platform evaluation of digital communication effectiveness.

This study differs in motivation and findings by addressing these gaps through a comprehensive, data-driven analysis of engagement effectiveness across Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and LinkedIn. Unlike previous research, which often assesses engagement based on a single metric or within a limited timeframe, this study examines the interplay between engagement rate (ER), Click-Through Rate (CTR), and conversions, incorporating recent algorithmic changes and user behaviour shifts from 2022 to 2024. Additionally, while past research has predominantly focused on influencer marketing, this study evaluates the combined impact of interactive content, micro-influencers, and content adaptation strategies in shaping audience interaction. The findings

contribute to a deeper understanding of platform-specific engagement strategies and provide practical recommendations for optimizing digital communication strategies for brand promotion. The analysis of the literature shows that the effectiveness of digital communications depends on the adaptation of brands to platforms, taking into account the specifics of the audience, as well as the use of new technologies and analytical tools for successful marketing strategies.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research design

The study consisted of three stages aimed at analysing the effectiveness of digital communications in promoting brands on social media platforms. The first stage was a theoretical analysis of the literature, in particular, approaches to measuring effectiveness and methods for analysing activity on platforms (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, TikTok). This allowed us to identify key performance indicators (KPIs) - reach, interaction, CTR, and conversions. The second stage provided for collecting data on these indicators from public analytical platforms and social media application programming interfaces (APIs), in particular for campaigns with organic and paid content. The third stage included quantitative and qualitative processing of the collected data, analysis of correlations between audience activity and conversions, as well as content analysis of successful publications to identify factors contributing to engagement.

3.2. Methods

The work used three main methods:

3.2.1. Quantitative analysis

Applied to assess changes in key digital communications performance indicators, such as ER, CTR, and conversions. The analysis was based on the data collected using social media platform APIs (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok) for 2022–2024. For example, the average ER on the Instagram platform for selected brand accounts increased from 4.2% in 2022 to 5.8% in 2024 after the implementation of interactive content. Quantitative analysis was conducted for Pearson correlation was used to determine the relationship between audience activity and conversions. The correlation formula:

$$r = \frac{\sum(X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum(X_i - \bar{X})^2 * \sum(Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}} \quad (1),$$

where:

- X – number of interactions (in thousands);
- Y – number of conversions (in thousands);
- r – correlation coefficient, ranging from -1 to +1 (where +1 means a strong positive relationship, 0 – no relationship, -1 – strong negative relationship).

3.2.2. Sociological surveys

An online survey of social media users (n=1200) was conducted between February and April 2024. The survey was conducted using Google Forms and Qualtrics platforms. Respondents were stratified by age, gender, and platform. Participants were recruited through targeted advertising on social media (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok) and LinkedIn. The survey included 25 questions, 20 of which were closed and 5 were open for additional comments. The main questions were related to interaction with branded content, trust in advertising, and the influence of social media on purchasing decisions. The results showed that 68% consider interactive content among TikTok users, such as videos with polls or games, effective in increasing brand trust, while this figure was only 35% for LinkedIn.

3.3. Comparative analysis

The method for comparing the effectiveness of digital communications strategies included analysis across platforms (Instagram vs. TikTok) and industries (fashion vs. technology). The results showed that interactive content and micro-influencers have a greater impact on fashion (7.2% of interactions) than on technology (4.1%). TikTok generates more video views, while LinkedIn provides a higher level of professional engagement. This approach provided a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of digital communications and the identification of key success factors on social platforms.

3.4. Sample

Five popular social platforms were selected for the study: Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and LinkedIn, which have different target audiences and algorithms. Facebook assesses the impact of different content formats due to its large audience, and Instagram - a high ER among young people. TikTok was selected due to the popularity of short videos and interactive formats, Twitter — for analysing text content for a professional audience, and LinkedIn — for assessing the effectiveness of brands in a corporate environment. The sample includes brand accounts with active campaigns in 2022-2024 using both organic and advertising content, with representatives of different

industries (fashion, technology, services). Table 1 shows the key characteristics of the selected platforms, including the type of content, the average ER, and the main audience.

Table 1: Characteristics of the Selected Platforms

Platform	Content Type	Average ER (2024)	Main Audience
Facebook	Text, photo, video	4.20%	Broad, 18–65 years old
Instagram	Photo, Video, Stories	5.80%	Youth, 16–35 years old
TikTok	Short videos	7.40%	Gen Z, 13–30 years old
Twitter	Text, photo, links	2.90%	Informed Audience, 25–50 years old
LinkedIn	Text, articles	3.50%	Professionals, 25–60 years old

Source: created by the author based on platform data and independent research for 2024.

The study used Microsoft Excel tools to analyse quantitative data (ER, CTR, conversions), Tableau to visualize and analyse content engagement trends, and a correlation formula to determine the relationship between digital communications characteristics and performance indicators. This methodology ensured the accuracy of the results and the representativeness of the analysis for the purpose of drawing informed conclusions about the effectiveness of digital communications.

4. RESULTS

The 2022-2024 study showed the variability of digital communication effectiveness across social media platforms. TikTok had the highest ER (7.4%) due to personalized algorithms

and Gen Z engagement. Instagram grew from 4.2% to 5.8% thanks to interactive content and micro-influencers. Facebook remained stable at 4.2%, but due to limited innovation. LinkedIn had 3.5%, being effective in professional communications, but with lower emotional engagement. Twitter showed the lowest engagement rate (2.9%) because of text-based content and lower activity. Posts during peak hours (6:00 PM–8:00 PM) generated 30% more views, and TikTok showed the highest ER in the evening (10.5%).

Table 2 compares the average ERs and KPIs across five selected social media platforms, reflecting key trends and differences in digital communications.

Table 2: Dynamics of ER indicators across social platforms

Year	Facebook (ER, %)	Instagram (ER, %)	TikTok (ER, %)	Twitter (ER, %)	LinkedIn (ER, %)
2022	4.2	4.2	6.8	3.0	3.4
2023	4.2	5.5	7.2	2.9	3.5
2024	4.2	5.8	7.4	2.9	3.5

Source: developed by the author based on the data from social media platforms and independent research for 2024.

The dynamics of the ER on the platforms for 2022–2024 show significant differences. TikTok leads due to interactive content and a youth audience. Instagram also shows growth due to visual content and micro-influencers. Facebook and Twitter remain stable or decrease their indicators because of limited innovation in content. LinkedIn has a moderate ER, remaining stable due to a professional audience.

Figure 1 compares the ER on the five main social platforms for 2022–2024, which gives grounds to assess the dynamics of the effectiveness of digital communications in promoting brands.

Figure 1 shows the ER dynamics on five platforms (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, LinkedIn) for 2022–2024. TikTok maintains the highest figures, growing from 6.8% to 7.4%, thanks to interactive content and popularity among young people. Instagram increased its engagement level from 4.2% to 5.8%, thanks to micro-influencers and interactivity. Facebook is stable at 4.2%, LinkedIn maintains a level of 3.4–3.5%, focusing on professionals. Twitter decreased its ER from 3.0% to 2.9%. The data shows growth on TikTok and Instagram, stability on Facebook and LinkedIn, and regression on Twitter.

Figure 1: Comparison of ER on social platforms, 2022–2024

Source: developed by the author based on the data from social media platforms and independent research for 2024.

Table 3 shows the key characteristics of the platforms and their impact on ERs.

Table 3: Key characteristics of the platforms and their impact on engagement levels, 2024

Platform	Main Audience	Content Type	Average engagement rate (2024)
Facebook	Broad, 18–65 years old	Text, photo, video	4.2
Instagram	Youth, 16–35 years old	Photo, video, stories	5.8
TikTok	Gen Z, 13–30 years old	Short videos	7.4
Twitter	Informed audience, 25–50 years old	Text, photo, links	2.9
LinkedIn	Professionals, 25–60 years old	Text, articles	3.5

Source: developed by the author based on the data from social media platforms and independent research for 2024.

Analysis of the characteristics of social media platforms shows significant differences in their impact on engagement. With the highest score of 7.4% in 2024, TikTok effectively uses short videos and interactive formats, attracting Generation Z. Instagram (5.8%) successfully uses visual content and micro-influencers. Facebook is stable at 4.2%, but is losing ground because of limited adaptation to new formats. LinkedIn delivers 3.5%, targeting a professional audience. Twitter has the lowest engagement rate at 2.9%, due to a decrease in activity and text-based content.

Figure 2 illustrates each platform’s share of the overall ER, demonstrating how different types of content and audiences affect the effectiveness of digital communications.

Figure 2 shows the ER on the five major social platforms in 2024. TikTok leads with 7.4%, driven by its popularity among young people and interactive content. Instagram ranks second with 5.8%, driven by new formats such as stories and

video. Facebook remains stable at 4.2%, targeting a broad audience but has limited innovation.

Figure 2: Distribution of ER on social platforms, 2024
Source: developed by the author based on the data from social media platforms and independent research for 2024.

LinkedIn reaches 3.5%, targeting a professional audience, and Twitter has the lowest rate at 2.9%, driven by text-based content and a decline in activity.

Table 4 shows the level of adaptation of social platforms to current trends and their impact on ERs in 2024.

Table 4: Level of adaptation of platforms to current trends and their impact on ERs, 2024

Platform	Level of adaptation to current trends (%)	Average ER (2024)	Main audience (age range)
Facebook	50	4,2	18–65 years
Instagram	85	5,8	16–35 years
TikTok	95	7,4	13–30 years
Twitter	40	2,9	25–50 years
LinkedIn	60	3,5	25–60 years

Source: developed by the author based on the data from social media platforms and independent research for 2024.

The results in Table 4 show that platforms that are better at adapting to new trends have higher ERs. TikTok, with 95% adoption, leads with 7.4% engagement thanks to interactive content and personalized algorithms. Instagram, with 85% adoption, reaches 5.8%, using innovative formats such as stories and reels. Facebook, with 50% adoption, maintains a stable result (4.2%), but has limited dynamics because of the lack of new formats. LinkedIn, with 60% adoption, has moderate engagement (3.5%), focusing on a professional audience. Twitter, with the lowest adoption (40%), has the lowest ER (2.9%), indicating the need for a strategy update.

Table 5 presents a comparison of the Social Progress Index (SEI) and Open Budget Index in the studied countries.

Figure 3 shows the impact of social engagement (Social Engagement Index) and content innovation on platform performance in 2024. The

figure provides an insight into the relationship between audience activity and the adaptation of platforms' content strategies to current trends.

Table 5: Comparison of social engagement indicators and the level of innovative content on platforms, 2024

Platform	SEI	Content Innovation Level (%)
Facebook	60	50
Instagram	85	85
TikTok	95	95
Twitter	45	40
LinkedIn	70	60

Source: developed by the author based on the data from social media platforms and independent research for 2024.

Figure 3. The impact of social interaction and the level of innovative content on platform effectiveness, 2024
Source: developed by the author based on the data from social media platforms and independent research for 2024

Figure 3 shows the relationship between the level of social engagement (SEI) and content innovation on platforms in 2024. Platforms with a high level of trend adaptation show better results. TikTok, with 95% adaptation, has an SEI of 95% and leads thanks to content innovation. Instagram, with 85% adaptation, has an SEI of 85%, using interactive content. Facebook, with 50% adaptation, has an SEI of 60%, indicating limited innovation efficiency. LinkedIn shows an SEI of 70% and innovation of

60%, and Twitter, with the lowest innovation (40%), has an SEI of 45%. The calculation of the Pearson correlation indicates a strong relationship between content innovation and SEI ($r=0.92$), as well as between SEI and trend adaptation ($r=0.87$). This indicates that innovation in content contributes to the growth of platform efficiency. Figure 4 shows a correlation model between the content innovation level and the social ER, illustrating the relationship between these indicators.

Figure 4: Correlation model between content innovation and social ER

Source: developed by the author based on the data from social media platforms and independent research for 2024

The model shows a positive relationship between content innovation and social engagement. The forecast based on correlation analysis indicates a possible increase in engagement. It is expected that platforms with a low level of innovation, such as Twitter, can increase ERs by up to 60% if interactive

content is adapted. Platforms with a medium level, such as Facebook, can reach 70% by investing in new formats and content personalization.

Figure 5 shows the projected changes in ERs on social platforms by 2028 at the current pace of implementing innovative content strategies.

Figure 5. Projected changes in the ER across platforms by 2028

Source: developed by the author based on the data from social media platforms and independent research for 2024.

TikTok is expected to maintain an ER of 7.4–8.2% by 2028 due to content innovation, Instagram will increase engagement to 6.5% due to interactive and visual formats, Facebook will reach 5.0% due to adaptation to new trends, Twitter will improve to 4.5% by modernizing content, and LinkedIn can reach 4.0% due to the use of multimedia elements.

The results showed that youth brands and consumer goods are easiest to promote on TikTok due to interactivity, premium brands and eco-friendly products on Instagram due to visual appeal,

as well as local initiatives and services on Facebook due to effective local targeting. Problems arose when promoting B2B brands on TikTok because of the low level of professional audiences and highly specialized services on Instagram because of limited targeting capabilities. The sample was based on representativeness for each platform for the purpose of comparing the effectiveness of communications across industries. Figure 6 shows the effectiveness of brand promotion on TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter in terms of ER, Conversion Rate (CR), and CTR.

Figure 6: Effectiveness of brand promotion on different platforms

Source: developed by the author based on the data from social media platforms and independent research for 2024.

The analysis showed that the effectiveness of brand promotion depends on the type of brand and platform. Youth brands have the highest ER (12–15%) on TikTok thanks to short videos and influencer marketing. On Instagram, premium brands provide a Conversion Rate of 10–14% through Reels and photos, and Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) achieves a high ER through Stories (8%). Facebook is effective for local brands (CTR 5–7%) and educational services, but technology brands have a lower ER (3.5%). LinkedIn demonstrates high effectiveness for B2B brands, in particular technology (Engagement Rate 6–8%) and educational programmes (CR up to 9%). These success factors emphasize the importance of adapting content and marketing strategies to the specifics of the platform and target audience.

5. DISCUSSION

The study of the effectiveness of digital communications analysed the results of ten academic papers published in the last five years. The researchers [4] emphasize that interactive content on TikTok provides a high level of engagement due to personalization, which is confirmed by our data:

TikTok has the highest level of interaction (7.4%). The scientists [2] argue that adaptation to the specifics of the platform and the regularity of publications are key factors of effectiveness, which is also confirmed by our results for peak hours (18:00–20:00). The study [7] emphasizes the importance of LinkedIn for corporate brands, but our results show a moderate ER (3.5%), which does not give it an advantage over platforms with visual content. The authors [29] emphasize the integration of TV advertising and digital communications, but multimedia platforms showed a higher ER in our study.

The study of digital communication effectiveness analysed the results of ten academic papers published in the last five years. The authors [4] emphasize that interactive content on TikTok provides a high ER due to personalization, which is confirmed by our data: TikTok has the highest ER (7.4%). The researchers [2] argue that adaptation to the specifics of the platform and regularity of posting are key factors of effectiveness, which is also confirmed by our results for peak hours (6:00 PM–8:00 PM). The authors [7] emphasize the importance of LinkedIn for corporate brands, but our results

show a moderate ER (3.5%), which does not give it an advantage over platforms with visual content.

The scientists [29] emphasize the integration of TV advertising and digital communications, but multimedia platforms showed higher ER in our study. The authors [18] indicate that the emotional connection between a brand and consumers increases loyalty, as evidenced by the steady growth of engagement on Instagram and TikTok, which heavily use emotional content. The researchers [23] consider Twitter the most effective platform for engaging an informed audience, but our data showed that Twitter has the lowest ER (2.9%), indicating a loss of popularity of this platform. The authors [27] emphasize the importance of content focused on specific interests, as evidenced by the growth of Instagram engagement through micro-influencers targeting specific segments. The authors [20] argue that video formats increase engagement, and this is supported by the high performance of TikTok and Instagram.

The researchers [30] emphasize the importance of posting time for communication effectiveness, which is supported by our data: posting during peak hours (6:00 PM–8:00 PM) generated 30% more views, especially on TikTok with the highest ER (10.5%). The scientists [25] consider “likes” an overestimated performance indicator, whom we agree with, as our analysis used comprehensive indicators such as ER and CR. The researchers [31, 32] emphasize that innovative content increases campaign effectiveness, which is supported by our data, where TikTok and Instagram showed a steady increase in engagement due to adaptation to trends. Comparison with other studies confirms the importance of interactive, visual, and personalized content for high ERs, while Twitter and LinkedIn need to update their strategies.

5.1. Limitations

One of the main limitations of this study is its reliance on data from social platforms, which may not capture all interaction factors, such as private conversations or specific algorithmic changes. Furthermore, the study focused on only five major platforms (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, LinkedIn), which limits the generalizability of the results to other social media platforms, such as YouTube or Snapchat. Another limitation is the time frame (2022–2024), which does not account for the long-term impact of digital communications on brand promotion.

However, one limitation of this study is that it focuses only on engagement metrics, such as ER and CTR, without accounting for long-term brand

loyalty and customer retention rates. Additionally, while the study provides valuable insights into platform-specific effectiveness, it does not explore the impact of cross-platform integration strategies, which could further enhance digital communication outcomes. Future research should consider a broader scope of performance indicators and examine how combining multiple social media platforms contributes to overall brand success.

5.2. Recommendations

It is recommended to adapt content to the specifics of each platform in order to increase the effectiveness of digital communications in promoting brands, in particular, implementing interactive and visual formats that have proven effective on TikTok and Instagram. It is also necessary to develop flexible content strategies that take into account changing platform algorithms and trends. It is recommended to conduct additional studies that cover other platforms and a longer time period to better understand the dynamics of digital communications.

5.3 Difference from Prior Work and Study Achievements

This study significantly differs from prior research by offering a comprehensive cross-platform analysis of digital communication effectiveness in brand promotion. While previous studies have focused mainly on individual platforms or specific marketing techniques, this research compares Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and LinkedIn, identifying key success factors across diverse social media ecosystems. Existing literature often emphasizes either influencer marketing, algorithmic impacts, or content strategies in isolation. In contrast, this study integrates all these aspects to present a holistic understanding of engagement and conversion dynamics.

A key achievement of this research is its use of a data-driven approach, incorporating quantitative analysis, sociological surveys, comparative analysis, and correlation studies to evaluate the effectiveness of digital communication strategies. Unlike prior works that rely on general engagement theories, this study quantifies the impact of interactive content, micro-influencers, and posting schedules on key performance indicators (ER, CTR, and conversions). The findings provide actionable insights for businesses optimizing their social media strategies based on platform-specific characteristics.

Additionally, this study highlights the evolving nature of digital communications, particularly in how content adaptation and

innovative formats influence brand engagement. Prior research has often failed to account for rapid algorithmic changes in platforms like TikTok and Instagram. Focusing on 2022–2024 trends and predicting future developments until 2028, this study offers a forward-looking perspective that can inform long-term digital marketing strategies.

Furthermore, while existing studies overlook the impact of cross-platform marketing strategies, this research identifies the advantages and limitations of different platforms when combined. The findings suggest that brands must diversify their content approaches rather than rely solely on a single platform.

By addressing these gaps and presenting new insights, this study contributes to the ongoing digital marketing discourse, offering theoretical advancements and practical recommendations for optimizing brand engagement and conversions in the social media landscape.

5.4 Problems and Open Research Issues

Despite significant findings, several challenges and open research questions remain. Frequent updates to social media algorithms affect engagement rates and content visibility, requiring further research on the long-term impact of these changes on brand communication effectiveness. The increasing use of AI-driven personalization and automated content creation necessitates further evaluation regarding its influence on audience engagement, trust, and conversion metrics. Current research primarily focuses on individual platforms, while future studies should analyze how cross-platform integration enhances audience interaction and brand performance. Short-term engagement metrics such as ER and CTR provide limited insights into brand loyalty, making it essential to explore the long-term effects of digital communication on consumer retention.

Additionally, the effectiveness of micro-influencers compared to macro-influencers remains an open question, particularly regarding their impact on different industries and consumer trust. Ethical concerns related to data privacy, algorithmic bias, and targeted advertising continue to evolve, highlighting the need for research on how regulatory frameworks affect digital marketing strategies. Addressing these challenges will contribute to a deeper understanding of digital communication dynamics and optimizing social media marketing strategies.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study confirm that the effectiveness of digital communications in promoting brands largely depends on the adaptation of content to the specifics of each platform and the active implementation of innovative formats. The TikTok and Instagram platforms showed the highest ERs in 2024 (7.4% and 5.8%, respectively), which indicates their ability to effectively engage the audience through interactive and visual content. In contrast, Facebook and Twitter demonstrate stable or even decreased ERs (4.2% and 2.9%, respectively), which is due to the limited innovativeness of content formats and the specifics of the audience. LinkedIn, with an average ER (3.5%), confirms its effectiveness in professional communications. The academic novelty of the study lies in identifying the relationship between the level of adaptation of platforms to modern trends and the effectiveness of their content strategies. The correlation analysis established that the level of innovative content has a direct positive impact on social interaction rates ($r = 0.92$).

The scientific contribution of this study is developing a comprehensive framework for assessing the effectiveness of digital communications across multiple social media platforms. Unlike previous research, this study provides a cross-platform comparative analysis, identifying key performance indicators (ER, CTR, and conversions) and their correlation with content strategies. The research highlights the role of interactive content and micro-influencers in increasing audience engagement and offers a predictive model for future digital marketing trends until 2028. These findings contribute to academic literature and practical applications, equipping marketers with data-driven strategies to optimize brand promotion on social media.

This article significantly adds to the existing body of knowledge by bridging the gap between platform-specific engagement studies and cross-platform digital marketing effectiveness. Unlike previous research focusing on isolated aspects such as influencer marketing, SEO, or individual platform analytics, this study integrates multiple perspectives to present a more holistic approach to digital communication strategies. Moreover, it introduces a data-driven correlation model that quantifies the impact of various content formats and posting strategies on audience engagement. By forecasting digital communication trends until 2028, this research provides insights into current brand promotion strategies. It serves as a

foundation for future studies on the evolving landscape of social media marketing. The practical value of the study is the possibility of using its results to optimize brands' digital communications strategies. In particular, the results can be the basis for developing analytics tools that take into account the specifics of platforms and audience behavioural characteristics. The obtained data can also be used to create recommendations for the implementation of interactive content formats and personalization of communications aimed at increasing the ER.

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